

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA T bearing USN 6SU20FC801 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUJITH C V bearing USN 6SU20FC802 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANWAYAKRISHNA P bearing USN 6SU20FC803 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIKA S NAIR bearing USN 6SU20FC804 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHIRA K K bearing USN 6SU20FC805 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIK O K bearing USN 6SU20FC806 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms REEBA JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20FC808 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA JACOB P J bearing USN 6SU20FC809 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms STEENA M T bearing USN 6SU20FC810 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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